

A transfer learning framework for crashworthiness analysis based on sphere projection and PointNN

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Abstract

In the early phase of vehicle development, car manufacturers need to ensure the compliance with strict safety requirements while facing the problem of low data availability. Aiming to support the engineers, we propose a transfer learning (TL) framework for crashworthiness. The design of the new product can be viewed as a broad modification of past ones. For this reason, an attractive concept to investigate is the development of a machine learning (ML) approach able to learn from past designs, transferring the acquired knowledge to the new ones. TL can serve to this aim. Here, we propose a TL framework and apply it to explicatory industrial crash examples. To allow the ML model to learn the topological differences between old and new designs, we propose two approaches: sphere projection- and PointNN- based TL. Both approaches enhance TL, which results in a powerful technique to extract valuable information from limited datasets.

1 Introduction

Vehicle safety is a critical aspect of automotive development. Achieving the necessary safety standards requires significant R&D investment. This is particularly true for conducting hardware crash tests, which are essential for the vehicle development, yet expensive due to their destructive nature [1].

In the early stages of the vehicle development, the physical prototype of the product of interest is not yet available and, therefore, the hardware tests cannot be performed. In this phase, engineers need to rely on finite element (FE) simulations to predict the crash performance of the product. These simulations, while crucial, are also computationally intensive and hard to validate. The challenge of the crash performance prediction is made even more complex by the limited data availability in the preliminary design phase. It is difficult for the engineers to make informed decisions, as the ultimate geometrical information and material properties of the new product are not yet available.

It can be recognized that new vehicle designs are often an evolution of existing ones [2]. A task worth of pursuing is, therefore, utilizing past development data to inform the development of future designs. Car manufacturers continuously store high amounts of data from hardware tests, FE simulations, and real-world accidents, which often remain unexploited. These historical data can guide the development of new models, ensuring that new generations of vehicles can benefit from the accumulated knowledge.

This work proposes a machine learning (ML) methodology to support engineers in the early phase of designing crashworthy vehicles, when data is scarce and prototypes are not yet available. The approach is based on transfer learning (TL), that emerges as a solution to bridge past and present data. TL leverages knowledge from previous tasks to improve the efficiency when solving new challenges [3]. In this work, we plan to utilize TL as a bi-fidelity tool, with past data serving as low-fidelity information, and limited, high-fidelity data referring to the current product under-development. The overall idea behind this work is to use the extensive low-fidelity data to enhance predictions for the new high-fidelity product.

In this study, we apply TL to predict the crash performance of crash box structures, which are crucial components for the vehicle crashworthiness [4]. FE simulations performed on existing crash boxes constitute our source domain, representing the low-fidelity, historical data; the sparse data obtained from the simulations of the crash box under current development forms the target domain, which is our high-fidelity dataset. The effectiveness of the TL methodology depends on the similarity between the source and target domain [5]. In our case, the two domains refer to different mechanical systems and geometries. This decreases the similarity between the domains, thus making the transfer of knowledge more difficult.

To address this challenge, we propose two approaches to enhance the TL framework: the sphere projection (SP) technique [6] and the PointCloud neural network (PointNN) architecture [7]. The SP technique allows to represent three-dimensional geometric data in the form of matrices. In this way, the TL algorithm learns to distinguish between the source and target domains; the PointNN architecture is utilized to directly learn the 3D representation of the components. This approach requires higher computational resources and provides predictions on new components by leveraging the knowledge gained from previous models. Our goal is to explore how these two approaches can support and enhance the transfer of knowledge between older and newer products.

Combining TL with SP and with PointNN, we aim to establish a framework that automatizes the decision-making process in the early stages of crashworthiness studies. Traditionally, this process heavily relies on the expertise of engineers. Our framework not only supports this process but also extends the utility of TL to various research fields, e.g. verification and validation, concept feasibility, robustness studies, etc.

2 Transfer Learning for industrial applications

Nowadays, ML technology shows great success across a wide range of real-world applications. Examples include image recognition [8], email spam filtering [9], natural language processing [10], etc. ML typically requires access to a large amount of training samples in order to be successful [11]. However, in industrial applications, acquiring enough data can be costly, time-intensive, and sometimes even unfeasible.

TL offers a promising solution to this issue. By utilizing the insights gained from previously completed tasks, TL aims at successfully completing a similar task. In other words, TL applies knowledge from models that were pre-trained on a distinct but related task to enhance learning in scenarios with limited data availability [12]. This differs from traditional ML models that are instead specifically trained for a unique purpose. TL process involves transferring the basic knowledge from a source domain to a target domain, under the assumption that there is similarity between the two. The source domain usually has a wealth of data, while the target domain may have different characteristics and less data available [13].

Techniques as fine-tuning, feature extraction, and domain adaptation are employed to adjust the source model to the specifics of the target domain [14, 15, 16]. These techniques are particularly useful when pre-existing source models are available, as these models have already learned the relevant features from large datasets. Using pre-trained models can save resources and provide an advantage for learning the target task. However, it is common in industry that the target task is far from any available pre-trained source model. In these cases, training the source model from scratch is the only viable choice.

The TL literature contains examples of both pre-existing source models and models trained from scratch being adapted to new tasks. The former approach is common for academic ML challenges, e.g. speech recognition or object detection, while the latter is typical in industrial settings, where the data collection process is more challenging. In this paper, we focus on the second case. In the recent years, researchers have developed custom source models tailored to various specific industrial needs.

In fault diagnosis, for example, TL is proven to be beneficial. In [17], researchers improve the rolling bearing fault classification by training a neural network (NN) on source tasks, and then adapting it to classify additional fault types in the target task. TL is also applied to gear transmission fault diagnosis [18]. In [18], a convolutional NN is first trained on natural images and then adapted to classify fault types using experimental data [19]. These works demonstrate the robustness of TL for fault diagnosis across different systems.

In manufacturing, TL helps to predict the process parameters for injection molding with limited experimental data. This is achieved pre-training a ML model on simulations [20], thus showcasing the ability of TL to bridge the gap between simulated and real-world data. In the field of crashworthiness, TL is utilized by means of a geodesic convolutional NN [21]. The process proposed in [21] heavily relies on the engineering expertise, and does not consider the transfer of knowledge across various vehicle models. Overall, these literature examples show that the effectiveness of TL in industrial settings is influenced by the quality of the source model and the similarity between the source and target domains.

The literature also reveals that TL can be successful when the source and target domain data come from mechanically different systems. This “across different machines” approach can involve transferring the knowledge from simulations to reality, or from the past to the future [22]. When the domains differ significantly, embedding geometric information into the ML model is crucial for TL to be effective. SP and PointNN are two effective approaches to merge geometrical information into the ML models.

SP is a dimensionality reduction technique that maps 3D data onto a sphere, simplifying the geometry while preserving the essential features [6]. This technique is effectively used for part detection and plausibility checks in industrial applications [23, 24], and consists in transforming a 3D geometry into a 2D matrix. The 3D geometry is projected onto a surrounding spherical surface, that is then unfolded to create a 2D matrix representative of the geometry.

Another approach for the embedding of complex geometries in ML applications is PointNet, a NN architecture that processes raw 3D point clouds directly, enabling the ML model to learn from the unprocessed geometric data [25]. Authors of [7] use PointNN, a modified architecture derived from the PointNet, in a TL melt pooling application. PointNN is first trained using low-fidelity analytically-collected data; then, the architecture is fine-tuned using a small size of high-fidelity simulation data. In this way, they construct an accurate correlation between the scalar settings of the simulation and the temperature field on the surface of the studied component.

In summary, the literature review reveals that TL can be a powerful approach to leverage historical data and bridge the gap between different mechanical systems, but the effectiveness of the transfer depends on the ability to properly encode the geometric information of the domains. SP and PointNet emerge as promising techniques to address this challenge and enhance the TL framework for industrial applications.

3 The case study: the crash box drop tower test

This paper focuses on the application of the TL framework to a simplified crash box drop tower test [4]. In the automotive industry, it is a key experiment for evaluating crashworthiness and for assessing the impact of the structure’s geometry on its energy absorption capability. A crash box is a structural component, typically made of high-strength steel or aluminum, located in the front or rear areas of a vehicle. Crash boxes absorb energy to protect the vehicle’s main body from extensive damage [26].

Figure 1: Representation of a crash box. The dotted lines show a three-cells crash box design.

FE simulations can replicate the drop tower crash test, offering a cost-effective and repeatable alternative to physical experiments. The FE model used in this study involves a crash box constrained at one end, with a rigid barrier impacting it at a velocity of -56 km/h in z-direction. The crash box is modeled with shell elements, and the crash performance is recorded in terms of force-displacement curve. For an extensive explanation of the simulations settings, we ask the reader to refer to a previous work of the author [27].

Four crash box designs, referred to as A, B, C, and D are used for this study. Their geometric characteristics are summarized in Table 1. The table shows that crash boxes A, B, and C are three-cells geometries, while crash box D is a single-cell one, see Figure 1.

Table 1: FE model parameters. t_n represents the nominal value of the thickness.

Design	a [mm]	b [mm]	t_n [mm]	# cells [-]
A	120.0	63.3	2.2	3
B	101.0	62.1	2.3	3
C	120.6	69.2	2.0	3
D	122.3	62.6	2.4	1

The simulations are run using the LS-DYNA solver, version R9.3.0. The input variables chosen for the study are the thickness t of the crash box and the overlap Ω between the crash box and the rigid barrier in x-direction. For a representation of t and Ω , we ask the reader to consult [27]. Sobol sequences is used as the sampling technique to vary the input parameters within their defined ranges, that are reported in Table 2. A total of 200 FE simulations are performed for each crash box design.

Table 2: Design space settings. The thickness t varies with a truncated Gaussian \mathcal{N} distribution with mean $\mu = t_n$ and standard deviation $\sigma = 0.074t_n$; the overlap Ω varies with a uniform \mathcal{U} distribution. The distributions are defined with a minimum-maximum range.

Parameter	Distribution
t [mm]	$\mathcal{N} [t_n - 0.05t_n ; t_n + 0.05t_n]$
Ω [mm]	$\mathcal{U} [-(3/10)a ; +(3/10)a]$

4 Methodology

A previous work of the author [28] proposes a TL framework for crashworthiness divided into four steps: data collection, data preparation, TL implementation, and evaluation of the results. This section focuses on the implementation of two approaches to enhance the data preparation step of the same work [28]. The first enhancement involves the use of the SP technique, and the second utilizes the PointNN architecture.

In [28], the TL methodology consists of identifying the variants of the mechanical system constituting the source and the target domains, training the source model, and then fine-tuning it to the target domain data. While we refer the reader to [28] for the main details of the TL procedure, here we focus on enhancing the translation of the variant information into ML-readable inputs. The implementation of the SP and PointNN approaches is carried out in PyTorch.

The SP technique allows to represent 3D geometric data in the form of 2D matrices. We implement the SP process following three steps: (i) the nodes of the 3D geometry are projected onto a surrounding spherical surface, which is divided into pixels, (ii) the number of nodes per spherical pixel is summed, and (iii) the sphere is unfolded creating a 2D matrix,.

The 2D matrix obtained from this process is then used as input to the TL algorithm, specifically to a CNN architecture. The CNN is first trained on the source domain data, and then its weights are adapted to the

limited target domain data. This is achieved through a fine-tuning procedure like the one explained in [29]: some layers are kept frozen, and others are left free to readapt to the target domain instances. Depending on the structure of the CNN, the output can be a scalar value representing a specific crash performance metric, e.g. the maximum force, or a vector of multiple metrics. The performance of the SP-enhanced TL approach is evaluated by comparing it to a CNN trained exclusively on the target domain data, which represents the prediction that would be obtained without the use of TL.

In parallel to the SP-enhanced TL approach, this work explores the use of the PointNN architecture to directly learn the crash performance of the mechanical system of interest. We plan to exploit the PointNN architecture to predict the displacement field of the structure of interest. The internal structure of the PointNN is based on the one explained in [7]. The output of our PointNN architecture is a $N \times 4$ matrix, where N is the number of nodes, and the columns represent the x , y , z coordinates of the undeformed node locations and the displacement d of each node, Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the inputs and outputs of the PointNN architecture [7].

The two inputs of our PointNN architecture are: (a) a $N \times 3$ matrix containing the x , y , and z coordinates of the nodes of the interest structure, and (b) a vector of scalar values representing the input variables of the study. Following the procedure explained in [28], the PointNN architecture is first trained on the source domain data, leveraging the extensive information available from the past designs. Then, the trained model is fine-tuned using the limited target domain data, which corresponds to the current product under development.

5 Application

This section focuses on the application of the two approaches introduced in Section 4 to enhance the TL framework for crash box structures. For both the SP and PointNN approach, we study the influence of the input variables thickness t and overlap Ω on the crashworthiness of the structure. The crash boxes A, B, and C are considered as the source domain, and crash box D is the target domain.

The idea of the SP-enhanced TL for crash analysis was already presented in [29], where it is applied to bonnet structures. In the current work, we apply it to crash box geometries. With the SP approach, we aim to predict the maximum value F_{max} of the force-displacement curve registered as a result of the crash box drop tower simulation. The procedure for the implementation of the SP-enhanced TL follows the steps indicated in [28]. First, we collected and prepared the data, then we trained the source domain model, and finally we fine-tuned it to the target domain data.

In our specific case, the crash box and the rigid barrier were considered as a whole and projected together. In this way, we automatically embedded the overlap Ω information in the final matrix. We centered the points

of the crash box and barrier with respect to their center of gravity. Then, we performed principal component analysis on the centered 3D coordinates and created a matrix following the SP method, Figure 3. The sphere was constructed with 1296 pixels, resulting in a 36x36 matrix. Also the thickness information of the crash box was automatically encoded in our procedure: when summing the nodes per pixel, the final amount of nodes was multiplied by the thickness value t of the crash box in that specific simulation. At the end of the data collection procedure, each data sample was constituted by a matrix that contained information of both t and Ω , and the output scalar F_{max} .

Figure 3: Schematic representation of the SP procedure.

The source domain data was collected merging the data from the simulations for crash boxes A, B, and C. Afterwards, we split the data into training, validation, and testing sets with a ratio of 70%, 20%, and 10%, respectively. After scaling the data as showed in [28], we trained the CNN source domain model. The CNN consisted of three convolutional layers, followed by three fully connected layers, and a max-pooling layer. This model design was aimed at extracting the relevant features from the input data and learns a non-linear mapping between the input matrix and the output variable F_{max} . We implemented a custom loss function based on the Root Mean Squared Error and employed an early stopping strategy to prevent overfitting. The quality of the source domain model was good enough to proceed with the fine-tuning step, reaching an R^2 score of 0.98.

Figure 4: Results for the SP-enhanced TL.

TL was then performed using a limited amount of target domain data that belonged to crash box D. The results of the fine-tuning procedure were collected for different sizes of the target domain datasets, i.e. $N_t = [3, 5, 7, 10, 15, 17, 20]$ data points. This range of target dataset sizes reflects the assumption of low data availability for the domain of interest. For each training set size, we performed 20 independent runs, where the target domain dataset was randomly split into training, validation, and testing sets. During the fine-tuning process, we froze the whole source domain model except the last two fully connected layers. The R^2 scores for each of the 20 runs were stored. Figure 4 shows the results in terms of average R^2 score for the different

N_t values. Moreover, as explained in Section 4, the TL results were compared to those obtained with a CNN exclusively trained on target domain data. Figure 4 shows in blue the results obtained with TL, and in red the ones without it.

Figure 4 allows to observe that the more target domain data points are available, the more the quality of the prediction increases, i.e. the R^2 increases. This fits with the general expectation according to which, with less information from the target domain, it becomes more difficult to compute a good prediction. In addition, TL achieves higher R^2 values with respect to the assessment method. With only 5 data points, TL reaches an R^2 higher than 0.8, which can be considered a satisfactory prediction quality in the early phase of vehicle design. With $N_t = 20$, the methods with and without TL converge to the same quality. This suggests that for high N_t , TL does not provide any advancement with respect to exclusively using the target domain data.

The crash box example of Section 3 was also used to showcase the applicability of the PointNN-enhanced TL. Specifically, we used the PointNN architecture to predict the z-displacement field of crash box D, leveraging the same information coming from crash boxes A, B, and C. The final column of the PointNN output, i.e. d of Figure 2, represents the z-displacement values of the individual nodes that form the 3D geometry of the crash box. These displacement values were recorded in the time step that coincides with the elastic rebound of the structure.

In the PointNN implementation, we set the number of input nodes N to be 1024 for computational efficiency, although the original 3D crash box models contained over 3000 nodes. To preserve the important geometric details while downsampling, we employed a targeted approach. Specifically, we allocated 50% of the 1024 nodes to the upper third of the crash box height, where higher deformations are expected. The remaining 50% of the nodes were distributed across the lower two-thirds of the crash box height. This ensures that the critical regions of the structure are represented with a higher density of nodes in the downsampled point cloud input.

We used this targeted downsampling to also augment the size of the original simulation dataset. From a single simulation, we repeatedly randomly selected 1024 nodes from the full 3D geometry. Following this approach, we generated a total of 20 samples from each single crash box simulation. This data augmentation strategy allowed us to reach a pool of 600 source domain samples.

Figure 5: Results for the PointNN-enhanced TL.

To train the source model, we modified the PointNN architecture of [7] to fit it to our input and output spaces. The quality of the trained source domain model was evaluated in terms of the average R^2 score across all the predicted nodes, and was equal to 0.85. The fine-tuning was then implemented modifying the trained source model by means of the limited target domain data of crash box D. During the fine-tuning process, only the fully connected layers within the TNet blocks of the PointNN [7] and the final convolutional layer were updated, while the rest of the architecture was kept frozen. The effectiveness of the PointNN-enhanced TL was tested using different sizes of the target domain dataset, $N_t = [0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 32]$. For comparison,

we also implemented an assessment method that simply used the pre-trained source model to directly predict the z-displacement field of the target crash box D, without any fine-tuning.

Figure 5 shows the results in terms of the average R^2 score across all the predicted nodes for both TL in blue and the assessment method in green. The assessment method shows a constant R^2 of 0.78, as it does not incorporate any target domain information. The PointNN-enhanced TL outperforms the assessment method with higher values of R^2 . The prediction quality improves as more target domain samples N_t are available for fine-tuning, reaching an R^2 of 0.89 with just 10 target domain simulations. This demonstrates that the TL approach can effectively leverage the knowledge from the source crash box designs A, B, and C, thus enhancing the predictions for the target crash box D, even with a limited amount of high-fidelity data.

When $N_t = 0$, the TL results coincide with the prediction of the source domain model alone, which already exhibits a good R^2 of 0.78 on the target testing data. This suggests that the z-displacement fields of the source and target crash box designs are sufficiently similar, allowing the source model to provide a reasonably accurate prediction on the target domain without any fine-tuning. However, the additional computational effort to fine-tune the source model to the target domain further improves the prediction quality, highlighting the benefits of the TL framework.

6 Conclusion

This paper presented a TL framework to support the early phase of vehicle development, when data availability is limited, and physical prototypes are not yet available. The goal was to leverage the extensive historical data from past vehicle designs to enhance the predictions for new product development. Two approaches were introduced to enhance the TL process by incorporating geometric information: the SP technique and the PointNN architecture.

The main results of this work demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed TL framework in the context of crashworthiness analysis. Both the SP-enhanced TL and the PointNN-enhanced TL outperformed the assessment methods in their respective tasks. This result highlights the benefits of the TL framework in leveraging knowledge from past designs to improve the predictions for new crash box geometries.

This work also revealed some challenges that need to be further investigated. The application of the TL framework to complex assembled structures, rather than single components, may introduce complexities. Additionally, the number of pixels used in the SP method, as well as the downsampling procedure for the PointNN approach, can significantly impact the quality of the results and the computational effort required. A further exploration of these aspects is required to understand how to achieve the best predictive performance.

Continuing the research on embedding complex geometric data into ML models, potentially exploring alternative methodologies beyond SP and PointNN, could further enhance the applicability of TL in the early stages of vehicle development, where data is scarce, and engineering expertise is crucial. Overall, this work has demonstrated the promising potential of TL for crashworthiness analysis, particularly when combined with techniques that can effectively encode geometric information. The proposed enhanced TL framework can provide valuable support to engineers, thus helping them in making informed decisions during the critical early phases of vehicle design.

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